

ROLE OF ACTUALIZING AGENT IN SPEECH

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Abstract. *This article discusses and analyzes the role of the actualizing agent in speech and the development of its speech.*

Keywords: *actualization, speech, functional, pronunciation, phonetic, native language.*

РОЛЬ АКТУАЛИЗИРУЮЩЕГО АГЕНТА В РЕЧИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается и анализируется роль актуализирующего агента в речи и развитии ее речи.*

Ключевые слова: *актуализация, речь, функционал, произношение, фонетика, родной язык.*

Development of each style in standard English and Uzbek languages predetermined by the change in their norms. This is also greatly influenced by changes in social conditions, scientific progress and the development of cultural life.

Traditional distinguishing functional styles are scientific (Popular Science), formal, publicistic (popular), colloquial, artistic — language subsystems, each of which is unique at five main levels: phonetic, morphological, lexical, syntactic and it has features in terms of text content.

Functional styles are characterized by the fact that it is possible or impossible to use one or another elements and structures, as well as their communication systems. For example, phonetic tools are important for the oratory style: adherence to pronunciation standards, wide use of intonation; syntactic for the scientific style: clear syntactic structure, direct word order, wide application of words, wide application from various specific and specific systems, at the text level: logical, clear presentation structure (newspaper or magazine article). The text of the formal style is characterized by the presence of special terms (commercial, legal, etc.), stamps, specialized foreign expressions, abbreviations, mixed words, the absence of figurative means at the lexical level; complex structures at the syntactic level are formed using the widespread use of sentences in the majhul ratio of the verb. Functional styles are found in both written and oral form. The colloquial style is characterized by the presence of short sentences, two-syllable words, phonetic and syntactic abbreviations. The artistic style combines three subordinate styles: the poetic style of language, the emotional (artistic) prose style, and the dramatic style. Each of these sub-styles and for a separate sub-style also have common features. Artistic texts also have a number of difficulties, since they combine logical-intellectual information with figurative-emotional information.

Reading texts in a popular style can be a challenge. It should be noted that the peculiarity of this style: one part of the texts is scientific, the other part — stands close to texts in other styles. Journalistic texts are characterized by covering political vocabulary, phraseological units, abbreviations, realities, newspaper prints, phrases and various topics. Newspaper and magazine publications have a variety of titles, including promotional and emotionally compelling. Two types of popular style are manifested in oral speech: the oratory style and the text of radio and television programs, as well as the newspaper style in written speech. Written forms of the popular style are essays (philosophical, literary, moral) and journalistic articles (political, social, economic, etc. The

general purpose of the publicistic style is to influence public opinion, convince the reader or audience that the comment made by the author is the only real one, and encourage it to accept the stated opinion. The popular style is classified by its clear and logical syntactic structure with the widespread use of conjunctive words and the fragmentation of the text into parts. Oratory style is an oral form of publicist style. Direct communication with the audience allows you to use the syntactic, lexical and phonetic features of written and oral speech. The peculiarities of this style are the direct appeal to the people; sometimes — characterized by the use of words related to the colloquial style. Stylistic means involved in the style of public speaking are determined by the communicative situation. The speaker often uses analogy and metaphors, but usually employs traditional methods, as individual stylistic devices can be difficult to perceive. Texts in the scientific style are aimed at promoting the achievements of Science and technology to a wide range of readers.

Usually materials are presented in an interesting and convenient way, using a certain amount of numerical data, formulas, diagrams and terms. To attract attention, repetition, rhetorical questions, appeal to the reader are widely used. Scientific text is usually characterized by an informative title, features that characterize the history of the issue or introduce the topic. The peculiarities of the scientific text are characterized by emphasized logic, repetition with additional arguments, complex syntax and professionally oriented topics.

The formal style is represented by different sub-styles or types: the language of business documents; the language of legal documents; the language of diplomacy; the language of military documents. The main purpose of these types of communication tools is to identify the conditions that connect the two parties and to reach mutual agreement between the two contracting parties. Another distinctive feature of this style is the direct use of words in their own sense. Figurative meaning does not apply in it.

Readers' speech is usually explained by the fact that they do not seek to beautifully express their opinion, their oratory thinking and lack of vocabulary. It is no secret that they make many mistakes in expressing their thoughts, whether in written or oral form, and also do not adhere to the culture of speech at all. K.I. Chukovsky's opinion: "...not only the reader, but in many people thoughts come to the surface in a messy, semi-sloppy, sleepy way".

Nowadays, it is considered necessary tasks for every native language teacher to form speech thinking in students, to comprehend the meaning of each pronounced word. Of course, the formation of speech thinking in students requires a long and hard work from the teacher, as well as methodological skill, practical experience and the ability to organize the lesson well. It is known that texts typical of the Uzbek people, many phraseological units are found in stories, readers understand their mere meanings, of course, in the context of the text. However, the head and moveable meanings of words in phrasemas are understood by them only through assignments based on lexicological analysis. In this process, it is necessary to use more phraseological units in the formation of speech thinking of students.

All units in the language have the property of multiple meanings. Examples of this include suffixes, words, and phrases. Before automating a language, it is necessary to convert all units in it as electronically as possible so that a solution to this problem is found. This work is not a process that increases in itself to practice. A lot of time and money is spent on automation. It is necessary to start the work by replacing the units that have initially assimilated into our language from

foreign languages with an alternative. This work has been tried in practice by scientists before, but has had an impact. The reason is that the tongue will never take the barely tucked units. This should be done as a result of a thorough analysis of the work slowly. Only then can the intended result be achieved.

In the plan to improve the effectiveness of speech development, it is important to conduct walks, trips not only for simple observations (observations) on surrounding objects, but also for their study.

At this point, we will have to figure out what can be achieved in the study of surrounding objects.

In the study of the environment (by educators or parents), children should not just observe, but also go to see the objects in their parts, elements and perceive processes, phenomena, and reflect on them. To achieve this, the educator is tasked with comparing, comparing, separating, generalizing, analyzing and using other similar methods. In addition, in the process of learning) it is important to attract preschool older children to the types of labor that are convenient for them (cleaning ditches, loosening the base of trees, caring for flowers). Such an approach is associated with the fact that when a person does something with his own hands, he will remember it more and more fully. With this method, shortcomings in the connecting speech of preschool older children are complemented by verbatim and recollection of the names of objects-objects.

The development of speech of preschool adults largely depends on the correct solution of the following things:

- didactic materials on the development of speech (speech of educators and parents aimed at a certain purpose, fairy tales, songs, stories that are read or told to children);
- methods and methods of Education used to master didactic materials;
- it is necessary that, relying on the content of the educational material, some methods of its study and the principles related to them, the educator plans all the work related to the cultivation of speech.

We came to the conclusion that in the process of conducting research work on the same problem, it is better to work on speech growth, relying on the following didactic principles:

- understanding the speech material for the teaching of the organs of speech as well as the hand;
- understanding the importance of speech and developing lexical and grammatical skills;
- assessment of speech expressiveness. To do this, it is advisable to choose didactic materials that develop a certain feeling in older preschool children;
- the gradual enrichment of speech.

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